

A Study Of Samskritha Varnamala

An Analysis of its Organisational Structure and Uses

Dr. Vijayalakshmi

M, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Sanskrit, MGM College, Udipi
vijayaamrutha@gmail.com

Abstract

Varnamala is the collection of Samskritha alphabets. It is not just collection of letters. But it is really like garland of letters which is organised in an attractive as well as in a systematic way. In other words, Varnamala is a scientific organisation of Varnas which are also called Aksharas. It introduces the vocal system. Place of sound production, efforts required, duration for which it is produced, pitch quantity of sound production are the key factors in the organisation of Varnamala. It clearly elaborates which areas of our vocal system correspond which sound. The paper intends to explore physiological use in uttering Samskritha letters; tries to identify usefulness recitation of Samskritha letters in Prana Therapy (Pranayama); discusses the relationship between Samskritha Varnamala and Yogic anatomy; and tries to explore the role of Samskritha Varnamala in tuning Speech Therapy. The study is descriptive in nature and based on the secondary data that is gathered from the books, and various research articles from journals. Paper finds that (i) Reciting Samskritha is like a brain massaging as there is a systematic touch of the tongue in all the different parts of our vocal system which in turn corresponds to the systematic touch in our brain of all those different alphabets. (ii) Very conscious use of breath in pronouncing Samskritha words especially महाप्राणाः, विसर्गः – that are aspirated alphabets - acts like a natural Pranayama. (iii) Different Nadis and Chakras in Yogic anatomy corresponds a particular alphabet or group of alphabets. Hence pronunciation of these alphabets stimulates and strengthens that particular part of the body. (iv) Different kinds of speech related disabilities are rectified through voice training programmes like repeated recitation of Varnamala, verses etc.

Key words - Samskritha Varnamala, Structure, Vocal System, Physiological Use, Pranayama, Yogic Anatomy, Speech Therapy

Introduction

वाचामेव प्रसादेन लोकयात्रा प्रवर्तते – Speech plays an important role in activating this world. It is an integral part of human life, Perhaps Acharya Dandi has rightly said this in the following verse.

इदमन्धतमं कृत्स्नं जायेत भुवनत्रयम् ।
यदि शब्दाह्वयं ज्योतिरासंसारं न दीप्यते ॥

‘All these worlds have been enveloped in the blinding darkness, had there been no language, brilliant light that shines eternally.’ This shows the utmost significance of language. It plays a

significant role in communication, in conveying desires and feelings, in inspiring human beings and in activating this world. But, Samskritha, the classical Indian language, stands unique from all other languages for its antiquity and unambiguity. It is a highly technical and systematic language is one of the most suitable languages for the computers. It is considered to be very efficient in making algorithms.

The word 'संस्कृतम्' – Samskritha is a compound word consisting of सं (good, well, perfected) and कृतम् (made, formed, work). It connotes a work that has been 'well prepared, pure and perfect, polished, sacred'. Samskritha is rich in vocabulary, phonology, grammar, and syntax, which remains undiluted to this day despite its antiquity.

Objectives:

The broad objectives of the paper are the following:

1. To study the process of speech production.
2. To understand the mechanism of the sound structure of Samskritha letters.
3. To study the vocal places and efforts corresponding to a particular letter.

Analysis:

In order to study Varnamala the mechanism of sound structure of Samskritha letters, we need to study the original source i.e., पाणिनीयशिक्षा. It deals mainly with the phonetics of Samskritha letters. Phonetics is the branch of learning which studies the production of sounds and their features for the purpose of linguistic communication. Some of broad themes studied in this field the places of articulations, the efforts of articulation etc.

Like any other languages Samskritha also has a collection of alphabets (speech sounds) which is called Varnamala. It is not just collection of speech sounds. But it is really like garland of speech sounds which is organised in an attractive as well as in a systematic way. Speech sounds are called Varnas or Aksharas in Samskritha. Hence, Varnamala is an organised structure of Varnas.

Varnamala:

Samskritha Varnamala is as follows –

- स्वराः – अ आ इ ई उ ऊ ऋ ॠ लृ ए ऐ ओ औ
- अयोगवाहौ – अं अः
- वर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि – क ख ग घ ङ
च छ ज झ ञ
ट ठ ड् ढ ण
त थ द ध न
प फ ब भ म
- अवर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि – य र ल व श ष स ह

This arrangement of speech sounds in Varnamala is on the basis of pace of production, efforts, time required to produce sounds, pitch quantity, sound material etc. It also gives a clear picture of the state of vocal cords, sound source and amount of air escape, nasality and the movement of larynx during the speech production. All these are discussed as under -

Places of Sound Production and Efforts:

Identification of vocal places of our body plays a significant role in the study of Varnamala. It introduces the vocal system. It clearly elaborates which areas of our vocal system correspond which sound. Basically, there are five places producing letters. They are -

1. कण्ठः – Throat - Speech sound produced in this place is called कण्ठ्यः – Guttural.
2. तालुः – Palate - Back of the tongue touches palate and also tongue touches the lower part of the gum area of lower teeth - Speech sound produced in this place is called तालव्यः – Palatals.
3. मूर्धा – Cerebrum - Tip of the tongue touches gently the centre of palate - Speech sound produced in this place is called मूर्धन्यः – Cerebral.
4. दन्ताः – Teeth - Tip of the tongue gently touches between the teeth - Speech sound produced in this place is called दन्त्यः – Dental
5. ओष्ठौ – Lips - Speech sound produced is ओष्ठ्यः – labial.

All the Samskritha speech sounds fall between these regions and Varnamala is the systematic way that the sounds have been organised. Let us see the speech sounds and corresponding vocal places.

Samskritha letters are classified as - स्वराः – vowels, अयोगवाहौ and व्यञ्जनानि – consonants.

स्वराः – vowels are the natural sounds that the human vocal produce. They are 22.

- ह्रस्वस्वराः – short vowels produced in one beat.
- दीर्घस्वराः – long vowels produced in two beats.
- प्लुतस्वराः – longer vowels produced in three or more beats.
- उदात्ताः – vowels rendered in the upper note.
- अनुदात्ताः – vowels rendered as perceived in the lower note.
- स्वरिताः – vowels rendered in the normal pitch note in one's voice.
- अनुनासिकाः – vowels pronounced nasally.
- अननुनासिकाः – vowels pronounced non-nasally.

Each speech sound is produced in a particular vocal part of our body. Speech sounds are organised as per the corresponding vocal places. All the 18 types of vowel अ are produced in throat. All the 18 types of vowel इ are produced in palate. All the 18 types of vowel उ are produced in lips. All the 18 types of vowel ऋ are produced in cerebrum. One unique sound that we see only in Samskritha is ऌ. It has no दीर्घ and its 12 forms are dental sounds. Then come diphthongs or compound vowels that combine two vowels. अ and इ joined together

produce the sound ए. अ and ए joined together produce the sound ऐ. There is no ह्रस्व sound to ए and ऐ and 12 types of the vowels ए and ऐ are produced in both throat and palate. अ and उ joined together produce the sound ओ. अ and ओ joined together produce the sound औ. There is no ह्रस्व sound ओ and औ; and 12 types of the vowels ओ and औ are produced in both throat and lips.

अयोगवाहौ are two - अनुस्वारः and विसर्गः and they are nasal and aspirated sounds respectively. They are अयोगवाहौ because they attain their selves when combined with other sounds like अ. Patanjali defines the terms 'Those sounds which are heard even though they have not been included in the Varnasamaamaya or so called Shivasutra. अनुस्वारः followed by the consonant क and ख is called जिह्वामूलीयः and it is produced in the bottom of tongue. विसर्गः followed by the consonant प and फ is called उपध्मानीयः and it is produced in lips.

Next set of speech sounds are व्यञ्जनानि - consonants. They are two types - वर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि and अवर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि. Usually, they are pronounced along with vowels. There are 25 वर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि and 8 अवर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि.

वर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि are the set of 5 classes and each of the class has 5 consonants. There is an element of touch and hence these are called स्पृष्ट (touch) sounds. Consonants spelled with little breath are called अल्पप्राणाः and consonants spelled with more breath are महाप्राणाः and nasalised consonants are called अनुनासिकाः.

- क्वर्गः - क ख ग घ ङ - कण्ठ्याः - These consonants are produced in throat region.
- चवर्गः - च छ ज झ ञ - तालव्याः - These consonants are produced in palate region.
- टवर्गः - ट ठ ड ढ ण - मूर्धन्याः - These consonants are produced in cerebrum region.
- तवर्गः - त थ द ध न - दन्त्याः - These consonants are produced in palate region.
- पवर्गः - प फ ब भ म - ओष्ठ्याः - These consonants are produced in lips.

In the above series, first and third sounds of each class are non-aspirated (अल्पप्राणाः), second and fourth sounds are aspirated (महाप्राणाः) and the fifth sounds are nasals (अनुनासिकाः). The nasal consonants continue to sound through the nose when the breath through the mouth has been stopped the tongue or lips. In addition, first and second sounds are voiced (घोषाः) and third, fourth and fifth sounds are unvoiced (अघोषाः). The unvoiced consonants have an explosive quality to them, whereas the unvoiced consonants have a gentle quality to them as though releasing the sound slowly. So, first two sounds in each class are कर्कश (hard) consonants and the last three sounds in each class are मृदु (soft) consonants. The logic in the organisation of the sounds in each class, thus, is -

Touch unvoiced non-aspirated

Touch unvoiced aspirated
 Touch voiced non-aspirated
 Touch voiced aspirated
 Touch voiced nasalised

Series of the classes is guttural, palatal, cerebral, dental and labial.

Last set of sounds are अवर्गीयव्यञ्जनानि which are not set under any group. य र ल व are semi-vowel (अन्तःस्थाः) and they are produced in palate, cerebrum, teeth, teeth-lips together (दन्तोष्ठम्) respectively. श ष स are sibilance (ऊष्माणः) – (figure of speech in which a hissing sound is created) and corresponding vocal places are palate, cerebrum and teeth. They are also called as fricative. ह is produced at throat and is pronounced with a forceful expulsion of air. It is a महाप्राण sound.

Difference between Vowels and Consonants:

The chief distinction between vowels and consonants is of the time required to produce it. Vowels need one Matraakala or more whereas consonants need half matraakala. Moreover, vowels are independent sounds whereas consonants are dependent sounds. In addition to it, vowels are अस्पृष्ट (untouched) sounds which means the sounds which are produced without touching any part of the speech producing organ. Whereas consonants are स्पृष्ट sounds because they are produced by contact with some parts of speech producing organs. Vowels sounds are free flowing sounds and one can intone it whereas consonants are mute sounds – they cannot be intoned.

Sanskrit speech sounds or Varnas and their corresponding vocal places are summarised in the Table No. 1:

Sl. No.	Vowels	Consonants	Vocal Place	Name of the Speech Sound
1	अ its 18 forms, विसर्गः	क ख ग घ ङ	कण्ठः	कण्ठ्यः
2	इ its 18 forms	च छ ज झ ञ	तालुः	तालव्यः
3	ऋ its 18 forms	ट ठ ड ढ ण	मूर्धा	मूर्धान्यः
4	ऌ its 18 forms	त थ द ध न	दन्ताः	दन्त्यः
5	उ its 18 forms, उपध्मानीयः	प फ ब भ म	ओष्ठौ	ओष्ठ्यः
6		ङ ञ ण न म	नासिका + कण्ठादयः	अनुनासिकः
7	ए ऐ and their 12 forms		कण्ठतालु	कण्ठतालव्यः

8	ओ औ and their 12 forms	कण्ठोष्ठम्	कण्ठोष्ठ्यः
9	व	दन्तोष्ठम्	दन्तोष्ठ्यः
10	जिह्वामूलीयम्	जिह्वामूलम्	जिह्वामूलीयः
11	अनुस्वारः	नासिका	

Table 1: Samskritha speech sounds and corresponding vocal places

Efforts in Speech Production:

Efforts for the production speech sounds are discussed, to some extent, in the above analysis. A detailed description of the same is given below. Efforts in the production of speech production is of two types – (1) आभ्यन्तरः Internal and (2) बाह्यः External. (These terms seem to be used by post-Paninian phoneticians, whereas Panini uses the terms आस्यप्रयत्नः and आनुपादानम् respectively.)

आभ्यन्तरः (internal) effort is the mode of articulation preparatory to the utterance of the sound. Here we get the five divisions and they are –

- (i) स्पृष्टः Contacted – there is touch of the tongue with the place of articulation. It is needed to स्पृष्ट sounds, i.e., sounds from क to म.
- (ii) ईशत्स्पृष्टः Slightly contacted – there is slight contact/touch of the tongue with the place of articulation. Semi-vowels (अन्तःस्थाः) i.e., य, र, ल, व C.
- (iii) ईषद्विवृतः Slightly open. Sibilants (ऋष्म sounds), i.e., श, ष, स, ह are produced using this effort.
- (iv) विवृतः Open. It needs the openness of the oral aperture. Vowels are produced using this effort.
- (v) संवृतः Tight or closed. Short अ is produced using this effort.

बाह्यः (external) effort is the mode of articulation at the close of the utterance of the sound. They are eleven – (i) विवारः (openness), (ii) संवारः (closure), (iii) श्वासः (breath), (iv) नादः (resonance), (v) घोषः (voice), (vi) अघोषः (voiceless), (vii) अल्पप्राणः (less aspirate), (viii) महाप्राणः (more breath/aspirate), (ix) उदात्तः, (x) अनुदात्तः, and (xi) स्वरितः. Three external efforts विवारः, श्वासः, अघोषः will be applicable for कर्कश consonants. Three external efforts संवारः, नादः, घोषः will be applicable for मृदु consonants. Rest is already elaborated in the previous part.

Research Questions

Having elaborated the Samskritha Varnamala following research questions are raised -

1. Is there any physiological use in uttering Samskritha letters?
2. How far are the practice and pronunciation of Samskritha letters useful in Prana therapy (Pranayama)?

3. To what extent is Samskritha Varnamala related with Yogic anatomy?
4. To what extent does Samskritha Varnamala tune Speech Therapy?

Methodology:

The study is descriptive in nature and based on the secondary data that is gathered from the books, and various research articles from journals.

Findings:

Main findings of the study in connection with the above research questions are as follows

—

Physiological Use in the Recitation of Samskritha Varnamala (Alphabets):

In order to provide precision of expression and sound the Sanskrit has elaborate system of phonetics which is deeply connected to human physiology. It is identified that there is a very big physiological use of recitation or pronouncing Samskritha alphabets.

The Samskritha alphabets and phonology are most scientific innovations based on human physiology. There is a systematic touch of the tongue in all the different parts of our vocal system which in turn corresponds to the systematic touch in our brain of all those different alphabets. While reciting particular alphabet, corresponding part in mouth and in brain gets stimulated. Hence reciting Samskritha is like a brain massaging.

Depending on the use of mouth organs, both the vowels and consonants have been divided into five categories, namely, gutturals, palatals, cerebral, dentals and labials. The group of gutturals are followed by palatal and so on in a systematic way. Gutturals are produced in the back of the mouth or throat. Palatals are produced with the tongue near or touching the hard palate. Cerebral are produced with the tip of the tongue hitting the top of the oral cavity. Dentals are produced with the help of the teeth and labials are produced with the help of the lips. Nasals are produced with the help of nasal cavity.

Efforts of articulation also determine play a prominent role in the organisation of Samskritha Varnamala. Efforts of articulation stand for the quality of air stream-volume, touching the wind pipe, vocal cord etc. आभ्यन्तरः (internal) effort inside the oral cavity and बाह्यः (external) effort is out of oral cavity, wind pipe etc.

Thus, it is clear that Samskritha Varnamala and phonology are most scientific innovations based on human physiology. It is widely believed that Samskritha Mantras when recited in the combination with sound vibrations, have specific effect on the mind and psyche of the individual. Alphabets in Samskritha Varnamala start from the gutturals, which are produced in first place of articulation; and are grouped and arranged systematically on the basis of series of the places and efforts of articulation.

In this regard it becomes noteworthy to quote the words of Peter Franklin Freund, who studied deeply Samskritha Varnamala system - “Generating evolution” is the goal of the program of reading the Samskritha Literature. This revered goal of raising life to perfection, unfolding the infinite potential of the human nervous system, is possible to attain, because the infinite dynamism of the Atma or Self, which is the energy, intelligence and organizing power

at the basis of the whole creation, is structured in the sounds of the Samskritha alphabet. (Peter Franklin Freund, Graduate School Maharishi University of Management Fairfield, Iowa VEDIC LITERATURE READING CURRICULUM July, 2006)

Samskritha Varnamala and Pranayama:

This is the second research question. We can observe very conscious use of breath in pronouncing Samskritha words especially महाप्राणाः, विसर्गः – that are aspirated alphabets. This usage of breath acts like a natural Pranayama. There is an inbuilt system of Pranayama in the Samskritha Varnamala. Mere recitation of sounds in Samskritha Varnamala starting from अ to ह begins the pranayama and it starts healing process. Destressing takes place unconsciously by the aspiration in pronouncing these alphabets. This sigh of relief is incorporated naturally in the Samskritha alphabets and their pronunciation.

In Samskritha Varnamala last sound starting from ह stands unique in the process of Pranayama, for it requires maximum breath release. Being a guttural sound, it comes from depth. When it is combined with some other sounds, it turns उरस्य, i.e., related to उरस् and comes from further depth. This experiment is undertaken by Dr. Sampadananda Mishra from Odisha (a renowned Sanskrit scholar and the Director of Sri Aurobindo Foundation for Indian culture, Puducherry). He made seven special combinations of ह and other consonants, and they are –

- ह + ण = ण्ह
- ह + न = ह्न
- ह + म = म्ह
- ह + य = ह्य
- ह + र = ह्र
- ह + ल = ह्ल
- ह + व = ह्व

These combinations of sounds give different experience when articulated correctly. It is his observation that if one repeats the above set for more than 25 cycles, an individual can start sweating. This is because. it makes natural Kapalabhati Pranayama. It is also very good for clearing the throat and other throat related problems. These seven sounds are known as उरस्य. उरस् means the chest and lungs. So, उरस्य means belonging to lungs. ह sound comes from the lowest depth and by combining it with the seven other sounds, it further extends depth. There are many words in Samskritha that are उरस्य. For example – अपराहः, पूर्वाहः, वहिः, चिहः, ब्रह्म, जिह्वः, ह्यः, बाह्वः, हासः, हृदः, आहादः, प्रहादः, आह्वानं, आह्वयः etc.

Pronunciation of विसर्गः also requires the release of air. The word derived from with prefix which means quitting, sending away. So, by pronouncing विसर्गः sound, one releases more air. By releasing air one can feel relaxed. So, विसर्गः is a complete relaxing sound and

makes the sound aspirant. It is similar to doing a short Kapalabhathi or Bahih-Kumbhaka Pranayama. So, when one says रामः, कृष्णः, देवः, शङ्करः, बालः etc. at the end is an extra gust of air out like Kapalabhathi or Bahih-Kumbhaka Pranayama.

Pronunciation of अनुस्वारः is akin to short Bhramari Pranayama. Inside a sentence, a trailing म् is written as Anuswara by putting a dot on the top of the alphabet if the word is not the last word in the sentence. For example – कृष्णं वन्दे जगद्गुरुम् – here कृष्णं has an ending dot, but जगद्गुरुम् has म् consonant. Every time one pronounces अनुस्वार, unconsciously he is performing a short Bhramari Pranayama (Inhale through both the nostrils. Exhale through both the nostrils and use the throat to make a soft sound, like the buzzing of the bee).

One more sound among the fricatives is जिह्वामूलीयः, i.e., विसर्गः preceded by क or ख. This is pronounced differently from विसर्गः. Here sound articulated from Nabhi or navel. This is akin to Bhastrika Pranayama. There are many such words with जिह्वामूलीयः sound, viz., दुःखम्; रामः कः?; कृष्णः कुत्र गच्छति? and verses like -

काकः कृष्णः पिकः कृष्णः को भेदः पिककाकयोः ।
वसन्तकाले सम्प्राप्ते काकः काकः पिकः पिकः ॥

Samskritha Varnamala, thus, closely connected to Pranayama, yields the benefits of Pranayama. One by pronouncing Samskritha Varnamala or verses unknowingly performs Pranayama. But one must pronounce these sounds consciously and in a proper way.

Samskritha Varnamala and Yogic Anatomy:

In the Yogic tradition the entire body is called शब्दशरीर or sound body. It is called so because Prana or Life-force or Life-energy flows through different energy currents in the body which are called Nadis. They are 72000 in number out of which Ida, Pingala and Sushumna are more significant. Yogis have captured the entire range of sound produced by these Nadis and divided them into fifty-one parts. They identified the approximate location of the sound. The point where two energy currents cross is called सन्धि (Sandhi), The point where three energy currents intersect is called मर्मस्थान (Marmasthana). There are about 52 Marmasthana in the body and each has its own sound.

Marmasthanas and corresponding sounds are listed in the table –

अ	Forehead	ख	Right Elbow	ध	Root of the Toes, Left Foot
आ	Face	ग	Right Wrist	न	Tip of the Toes, Left Foot
इ	Right Eye	घ	Root of the Fingers – Right Hand	प	Right side of the Torso

ई	Left Eye	ड	Tip of the Fingers – Right Hand	फ	Left side of the Torso
उ	Right Ear	च	Left Shoulder Joint	ब	Back
ऊ	Left Ear	छ	Left Elbow	भ	Navel
ऋ	Right Nostril	ज	Left Wrist	म	Stomach
ॠ	Left Nostril	झ	Root of the Fingers – Left Hand	य	Heart
लृ	Right Cheek	ञ	Tip of the Fingers – Left Hand	र	Top Right Shoulder
लृ	Left Cheek	ट	Right Hip Joint	ल	Between Shoulder Blades, just under Neck
ए	Upper Lip	ठ	Right Knee	व	Top Left Shoulder
ऐ	Lower Lip	ड	Right Ankle	श	Area from Heart to Right Hand
ओ	Upper Teeth	ढ	Root of the Toes, Right Foot	ष	Area from Heart to Left Hand
औ	Lower Teeth	ण	Tip of the Toes, Right Foot	स	Area from Heart to Right Toes
अं	Crown of the Head	त	Left Hip Joint	ह	Area from Heart to Left Toes
अः	Mouth	थ	Left Knee	ळ	From Heart to Orbit of the Face
क	Right Shoulder Joint	द	Left Ankle	क्ष	From Heart to Abdomen

Table 1: Speech Sounds and corresponding Marmasthanas

In the rituals, when they do अङ्गस्पर्श they touch different Marmasthanas in the body recite corresponding sound. This purifies and energises those locations. For example – the rituals of पापपुरुषनिःसारण and देहप्लावन, rituals of अङ्गन्यास in the recitation of Mantras, etc. The point where more than three energy currents cross is called चक्र (Chakra). This is where the sound is more obvious. Specific sounds are assigned to different Chakras. When one recites those sounds or Mantras, it purifies and energises concerned Chakra. The vibratory patterns of energy are more vibrant strong at the Chakras. At the centre of each Chakra, a distinct sound

predominates, and other distinct sounds are centred around it. Different Chakras and corresponding letters are as follows -

1. Vishuddha Chakra is located at throat. Sound हं at the centre. It has sixteen petals, and hence, produces sixteen sounds -

2. Anahata Chakra is located at the heart. It has twelve petals, and hence, produces twelve consonants -

3. Manipura Chakra is located at navel. It has ten petals, and hence, produces ten consonants -

4. Swadhisthana Chakra is located at genital organ. It has six petals, and hence, produces six consonants -

5. Muladhara Chakra is located at anus. It has four petals and hence, produces four consonants —

6. Ajna Chakra is located between two eye-brows. It has two petals and produces two sounds.

7. Sahasrara Chakra is located at the top of the head which contains thousands of petals.

In addition, the yogis have also discovered that every letter of the Samskritha Varnamala has its own colour, shape, presiding force, and unique transformative quality, as well as its own seer. They have also experienced the relationship between these sounds and different planets, stars, and constellations.

Samskritha Varnamala and Speech Therapy:

Speech disorders or disabilities related to articulation are dealt elaborately in Prathishakyas and Shiksha Granthas. Proper and conscious pronunciation of sounds are given much importance in these texts. Speech disorders may need medicinal treatment, surgical treatment or remedial training which are described in detail in Indian Ayurvedic Texts. A speech language pathologist plays a significant role in post-surgical remedies to a patient to enhance speech pattern of a patient. The Samskritha Varnamala, owing to its scientific, systematic and logical organisation and arrangement of speech sounds, becomes a valuable tool for evaluate the speech of a cleft palate patient. One of the distinct features of Samskritha alphabet is that its phonemes are phonetically exact and unaltered. Hence it is used to refine one's speech and identify the defects of the people in speech production. We have the examples of Dr. Sampadananda Mishra who cured the speech disorders through Sanskritha Varnamala. Conscious identification of places of articulation and conscious pronunciation of the sounds act as speech therapy.

People having difficulty to produce certain set of words can be treated with the practice of Varnamala. For example, Dr. sampadananada Mishra treated a girl having disability to produce the sound of class क with the help of Varnamala, some group of words like उत्कल, उद्गार and distinct verses. A verse with the letters having class क sounds can be utilised to rectify the disability in the production of class क sound –

अगा गाङ्गाङ्काकाकगाहकाघककाकहा ।
अहाहाङ्खगाङ्गागकङ्कागखगकाकक ॥

Here only one art of vocal cavity is active and it induces the active use of that particular place of articulation and hence, modifies the difficulty.

The disability in the production of labial sound (or a person with lazy lips) can recite the following verse in which only labial vowel is used along with consonants –

उरुगुं द्युगुरुं युत्सु चुकुशुस्तुष्टुवुः पुरु ।
लुलुभुः पुपुषुर्मुत्सु मुमुहुर्नु मुहुर्मुहुः ॥

Children with the problem of stammering etc. are treated by making them to recite Namaka-Chamaka, Mahishasuramardini Sthotra, Shivatandavasthotra, Vayusthuthi and such other beautiful verses. The choice of sounds in these verses are very useful in bringing clarity in articulation.

Conclusion:

Scholars and linguists agree that Sanskrit is the most scientific and systematic language; the world has ever known. The Sanskrit alphabets and phonology are most scientific innovations based on human physiology. It is widely believed that Sanskrit mantras, when recited in combination with the sound vibrations, have a specific effect on the mind and the psyche of the individual. Considering the exalted status of the language, the people who spoke Sanskrit were considered wise, well-educated and refined. Sanskrit as a language is itself refined and the Varnamala system in it is most scientific, systematic and logical. It is significant from linguistic, phonological as well as practical purposes.

References:

1. Peter Franklin Freund, VEDIC LITERATURE READING CURRICULUM, Graduate School Maharishi University of Management Fairfield, Iowa July, 2006)
2. Sri Swami Sivananda, The Science of Pranayama, A Divine Life Society Publication, 2000
3. Manomohan Ghosh, Paniniya Siksa, University of Calcutta, 1938
4. Mishra Sampadananda, Sanskrit and Speech Language, achieved from https://www.academia.edu/38924945/Sanskrit_and_Speech_Language_Pathology on 23rd December, 2022